

Citations of Predicting the Functional Effect of Amino Acid Substitutions and Indels (Cited Title)

Timespan:2013-2021.

Results found 1942
 Sum of the Times Cited 36540
 Average Citations per Item 18.82
 h-index 66

Title	Authors	Corporate Authors	Source Title	Publication Date	Publication Year	Volume	Issue	Beginning Page	Ending Page	Article Number	DOI	Total Citations
Standards and guidelines for the interpretation of sequence variants: a joint consensus recommendation of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics and the Association for Molecular Pathology	Richards, Sue; Aziz, Nazneen; Bale, Sherri; Bick, David; Das, Soma; Gastier-Foster, Julie; Grody, Wayne W.; Hegde, Madhuri; Lyon, Elaine; Spector, Elaine; Voelkerding, Karl; Rehm, Heidi L. Choi, Yongwook; Chan, Agnes P.	ACMG Lab Quality Assurance Comm	GENETICS IN MEDICINE	MAY 2015	2015	17	5	405	424		10.1038/gim.2015.30	9642
PROVEAN web server: a tool to predict the functional effect of amino acid substitutions and indels			BIOINFORMATICS	AUG 15 2015	2015	31	16	2745	2747		10.1093/bioinformatics/btv195	1036
The Human Gene Mutation Database: building a comprehensive mutation repository for clinical and molecular genetics, diagnostic testing and personalized genomic medicine	Stenson, Peter D.; Mort, Matthew; Ball, Edward V.; Shaw, Katy; Phillips, Andrew D.; Cooper, David N.		HUMAN GENETICS	JAN 2014	2014	133	1	1	9		10.1007/s00439-013-1358-4	856
The Human Gene Mutation Database: towards a comprehensive repository of inherited mutation data for medical research, genetic diagnosis and next-generation sequencing studies	Stenson, Peter D.; Mort, Matthew; Ball, Edward V.; Evans, Katy; Hayden, Matthew; Heywood, Sally; Hussain, Michelle; Phillips, Andrew D.; Cooper, David N.		HUMAN GENETICS	JUN 2017	2017	136	6	665	677		10.1007/s00439-017-1779-6	636
The somatic mutation profiles of 2,433 breast cancers refines their genomic and transcriptomic landscapes	Pereira, Bernard; Chin, Suet-Feung; Rueda, Oscar M.; Vollan, Hans-Kristian Moen; Provenzano, Elena; Bardwell, Helen A.; Pugh, Michelle; Jones, Linda; Russell, Roslin; Sammut, Stephen-John; Tsui, Dana W. Y.; Liu, Bin; Dawson, Sarah-Jane; Abraham, Jean; Northen, Helen; Peden, John F.; Mukherjee, Abhik; Turashvili, Gulisa; Green, Andrew R.; McKinney, Steve; Oloumi, Arusha; Shah, Sohrab; Rosenfeld, Nitzan; Murphy, Leigh; Bentley, David R.; Ellis, Ian O.; Purushotham, Arnie; Pinder, Sarah E.; Borresen-Dale, Anne-Lise; Earl, Helena M.; Pharoah, Paul D.; Ross, Mark T.; Aparicio, Samuel; Caldas, Carlos		NATURE COMMUNICATIONS	MAY 2016	2016	7				11479	10.1038/ncomms11479	624
Standards and Guidelines for the Interpretation and Reporting of Sequence Variants in Cancer A Joint Consensus Recommendation of the Association for Molecular Pathology, American Society of Clinical Oncology, and College of American Pathologists	Li, Marilyn M.; Datto, Michael; Duncavage, Eric J.; Kulkarni, Shashikant; Lindeman, Neal I.; Roy, Somak; Tsimberidou, Apostolia M.; Vnencak-Jones, Cindy L.; Wolff, Daynna J.; Younes, Anas; Nikiforova, Marina N.		JOURNAL OF MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTICS	JAN 2017	2017	19	1	4	23		10.1016/j.jmoldx.2016.10.002	534
dbNSFP v3.0: A One-Stop Database of Functional Predictions and Annotations for Human Nonsynonymous and Splice-Site SNVs	Liu, Xiaoming; Wu, Chunlei; Li, Chang; Boerwinkle, Eric		HUMAN MUTATION	MAR 2016	2016	37	3	235	241		10.1002/humu.22932	488

A comparative phenotypic and genomic analysis of C57BL/6J and C57BL/6N mouse strains	Simon, Michelle M.; Greenaway, Simon; White, Jacqueline K.; Fuchs, Helmut; Gailus-Durner, Valerie; Wells, Sara; Sorg, Tania; Wong, Kim; Bedu, Elodie; Cartwright, Elizabeth J.; Dacquin, Romain; Djebali, Sophia; Estabel, Jeanne; Graw, Jochen; Ingham, Neil J.; Jackson, Ian J.; Lengeling, Andreas; Mandillo, Silvia; Marvel, Jacqueline; Meziane, Hamid; Preitner, Frederic; Puk, Oliver; Roux, Michel; Adams, David J.; Atkins, Sarah; Ayadi, Abdel; Becker, Lore; Blake, Andrew; Brooker, Debra; Cater, Heather; Champy, Marie-France; Combe, Roy; Danecek, Petr; di Fenza, Armida; Gates, Hilary; Gerdin, Anna-Karin; Golini, Elisabetta; Hancock, John M.; Hans, Wolfgang; Hoelter, Sabine M.; Hough, Tertius; Jurdic, Pierre; Keane, Thomas M.; Morgan, Hugh; Mueller, Werner; Neff, Frauke; Nicholson, George; Pasche, Bastian; Roberson, Laura-Anne; Rozman, Jan; Sanderson, Mark; Santos, Luis; Selloum, Mohammed; Shannon, Carl; Southwell, Anne; Tocchini-Valentini, Glauco P.; Vancollie, Valerie E.; Westerberg, Henrik; Wurst, Wolfgang; Zi, Min; Yalcin, Binnaz; Ramirez-Solis, Ramiro; Steel, Karen P.; Mallon, Ann-Marie; de Angelis, Martin Hrabe; Herculat, Yann; Brown, Steve D. M.	GENOME BIOLOGY	2013	2013	14	7	R82	10.1186/gb-2013-14-7-r82	248	
Mutational landscape of gingivo-buccal oral squamous cell carcinoma reveals new recurrently-mutated genes and molecular subgroups	Maitra, Arindam; Biswas, Nidhan K.; Amin, Kishore; Kowtal, Pradnya; Kumar, Shantanu; Das, Subrata; Sarin, Rajiv; Majumder, Partha P.; Bagchi, I.; Bairagya, B. B.; Basu, A.; Bhan, M. K.; Chaturvedi, P.; Das, D.; D'Cruz, A.; Dhar, R.; Dutta, D.; Ganguli, D.; Gera, P.; Gupta, T.; Mahapatra, S.; Mujawar, M. H. K.; Mukherjee, S.; Nair, S.; Nikam, S.; Nobre, M.; Patil, A.; Patra, S.; Rama-Gowtham, M.; Rao, T. S.; Roy, B.; Roychowdhury, B.; Sarkar, D.; Sarkar, S.; Sarkar-Roy, N.; Sutradhar, D.	Int Canc Genome Consortium	DEC 2013	2013	4	2873	10.1038/ncomms3873	200		
The 100-genomes strains, an <i>S. cerevisiae</i> resource that illuminates its natural phenotypic and genotypic variation and emergence as an opportunistic pathogen	Strope, Pooja K.; Skelly, Daniel A.; Kozmin, Stanislav G.; Mahadevan, Gayathri; Stone, Eric A.; Magwene, Paul M.; Dietrich, Fred S.; McCusker, John H.	GENOME RESEARCH	MAY 2015	2015	25	5	762	774	10.1101/gr.185538.114	195

Exome sequencing identifies somatic mutations of DDX3X in natural killer/T-cell lymphoma	Jiang, Lu; Gu, Zhao-Hui; Yan, Zi-Xun; Zhao, Xia; Xie, Yin-Yin; Zhang, Zi-Guan; Pan, Chun-Ming; Hu, Yuan; Cai, Chang-Ping; Dong, Ying; Huang, Jin-Yan; Wang, Li; Shen, Yang; Meng, Guoyu; Zhou, Jian-Feng; Hu, Jian-Da; Wang, Jin-Fen; Liu, Yuan-Hua; Yang, Lin-Hua; Zhang, Feng; Wang, Jian-Min; Wang, Zhao; Peng, Zhi-Gang; Chen, Fang-Yuan; Sun, Zi-Min; Ding, Hao; Shi, Ju-Mei; Hou, Jian; Yan, Jin-Song; Shi, Jing-Yi; Xu, Lan; Li, Yang; Lu, Jing; Zheng, Zhong; Xue, Wen; Zhao, Wei-Li; Chen, Zhu; Chen, Sai-Juan	NATURE GENETICS	SEP 2015	2015	47	9	1061 +		10.1038/ng.3358	184
Next-Generation Sequencing of Pulmonary Sarcomatoid Carcinoma Reveals High Frequency of Actionable MET Gene Mutations	Liu, Xuewen; Jia, Yuxia; Stoopler, Mark B.; Shen, Yufeng; Cheng, Haiying; Chen, Jinli; Mansukhani, Mahesh; Koul, Sanjay; Halmos, Balazs; Borczuk, Alain C.	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY	MAR 10 2016	2016	34	8	794 +		10.1200/JCO.2015.62.0674	177
Contribution of Germline Mutations in the RAD51B, RAD51C, and RAD51D Genes to Ovarian Cancer in the Population	Song, Honglin; Dicks, Ed; Ramus, Susan J.; Tyrer, Jonathan P.; Intermaggio, Maria P.; Hayward, Jane; Edlund, Christopher K.; Conti, David; Harrington, Patricia; Fraser, Lindsay; Philpott, Susan; Anderson, Christopher; Rosenthal, Adam; Gentry-Maharaj, Aleksandra; Bowtell, David D.; Alsop, Kathryn; Cicek, Mine S.; Cunningham, Julie M.; Fridley, Brooke L.; Alsop, Jennifer; Jimenez-Linan, Mercedes; Hogdall, Estrid; Hogdall, Claus K.; Jensen, Allan; Kjaer, Susanne Krueger; Lubinski, Jan; Huzarski, Tomasz; Jakubowska, Anna; Gronwald, Jacek; Poblete, Samantha; Lele, Shashi; Sucheston-Campbell, Lara; Moysich, Kirsten B.; Odunsi, Kunle; Goode, Ellen L.; Menon, Usha; Jacobs, Ian J.; Gayther, Simon A.; Pharoah, Paul D. P.	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY	SEP 10 2015	2015	33	26	2901 +		10.1200/JCO.2015.61.2408	171
Comparative analysis of the domestic cat genome reveals genetic signatures underlying feline biology and domestication	Montague, Michael J.; Li, Gang; Gandolfi, Barbara; Khan, Razib; Aken, Bronwen L.; Searle, Steven M. J.; Minx, Patrick; Hillier, LaDeana W.; Koboldt, Daniel C.; Davis, Brian W.; Driscoll, Carlos A.; Barr, Christina S.; Blackistone, Kevin; Quilez, Javier; Lorente-Galdos, Belen; Marques-Bonet, Tomas; Alkan, Can; Thomas, Gregg W. C.; Hahn, Matthew W.; Menotti-Raymond, Marilyn; O'Brien, Stephen J.; Wilson, Richard K.; Lyons, Leslie A.; Murphy, William J.; Warren, Wesley C.	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	DEC 2 2014	2014	111	48	17230 17235		10.1073/pnas.1410083111	159

Solving Glycosylation Disorders: Fundamental Approaches Reveal Complicated Pathways	Freeze, Hudson H.; Chong, Jessica X.; Bamshad, Michael J.; Ng, Bobby G.	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF HUMAN GENETICS	FEB 6 2014	2014	94	2	161	175	10.1016/j.ajhg.2013.10.024	152	
Pericyte degeneration causes white matter dysfunction in the mouse central nervous system	Montagne, Axel; Nikolakopoulou, Angeliki M.; Zhao, Zhen; Sagare, Abhay P.; Si, Gabriel; Lazic, Divna; Barnes, Samuel R.; Daianu, Madelaine; Ramanathan, Anita; Go, Ariel; Lawson, Erica J.; Wang, Yaoming; Mack, William J.; Thompson, Paul M.; Schneider, Julie A.; Varkey, Jobin; Langen, Ralf; Mullins, Eric; Jacobs, Russell E.; Zlokovic, Berislav V.	NATURE MEDICINE	MAR 2018	2018	24	3	326 +		10.1038/nm.4482	151	
Recurrent DGCR8, DROSHA, and SIX Homeodomain Mutations in Favorable Histology Wilms Tumors	Walz, Amy L.; Ooms, Ariadne; Gadd, Samantha; Gerhard, Daniela S.; Smith, Malcolm A.; Auvil, Jamie M. Guidry; Meerzaman, Daoud; Chen, Qing-Rong; Hsu, Chih Hao; Yan, Chunhua; Cu Nguyen; Hu, Ying; Bowlby, Reanne; Brooks, Denise; Ma, Yussanne; Mungall, Andrew J.; Moore, Richard A.; Schein, Jacqueline; Marra, Marco A.; Huff, Vicki; Dome, Jeffrey S.; Chi, Yueh-Yun; Mullighan, Charles G.; Ma, Jing; Wheeler, David A.; Hampton, Oliver A.; Jafari, Nadereh; Ross, Nicole; Gastier-Foster, Julie M.; Perlman, Elizabeth J.	CANCER CELL	FEB 9 2015	2015	27	2	286	297	10.1016/j.ccell.2015.01.003	140	
Computational approaches in target identification and drug discovery	Katsila, Theodora; Spyroulias, Georgios A.; Patrinos, George P.; Matsoukas, Minos-Timotheos	COMPUTATIONAL AND STRUCTURAL BIOTECHNOLOGY JOURNAL		2016	2016	14		177	184	10.1016/j.csbj.2016.04.004	129
Genomic Profiling of Adult and Pediatric B-cell Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia	Liu, Yuan-Fang; Wang, Bai-Yan; Zhang, Wei-Na; Huang, Jin-Yan; Li, Ben-Shang; Zhang, Ming; Jiang, Lu; Li, Jian-Feng; Wang, Ming-Jie; Dai, Yu-Jun; Zhang, Zi-Guan; Wang, Qiang; Kong, Jie; Chen, Bing; Zhu, Yong-Mei; Weng, Xiang-Qin; Shen, Zhi-Xiang; Li, Jun-Min; Wang, Jin; Yan, Xiao-Jing; Li, Yan; Liang, Ying-Min; Liu, Li; Chen, Xie-Qun; Zhang, Wang-Gang; Yan, Jin-Song; Hu, Jian-Da; Shen, Shu-Hong; Chen, Jing; Gu, Long-Jun; Pei, Deqing; Li, Yongjin; Wu, Gang; Zhou, Xin; Ren, Rui-Bao; Cheng, Cheng; Yang, Jun J.; Wang, Kan-Kan; Wang, Sheng-Yue; Zhang, Jinghui; Mi, Jian-Qing; Pui, Ching-Hon; Tang, Jing-Yan; Chen, Zhu; Chen, Sai-Juan	EBIOMEDICINE	JUN 2016	2016	8		173	183	10.1016/j.ebiom.2016.04.038	127	

Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension: A Current Perspective on Established and Emerging Molecular Genetic Defects	Machado, Rajiv D.; Southgate, Laura; Eichstaedt, Christina A.; Aldred, Micheala A.; Austin, Eric D.; Best, D. Hunter; Chung, Wendy K.; Benjamin, Nicola; Elliott, C. Gregory; Eyries, Melanie; Fischer, Christine; Graef, Stefan; Hinderhofer, Katrin; Humbert, Marc; Keiles, Steven B.; Loyd, James E.; Morrell, Nicholas W.; Newman, John H.; Soubrier, Florent; Trembath, Richard C.; Viales, Rebecca Rodriguez; Gruenig, Ekkehard	HUMAN MUTATION	DEC 2015	2015	36	12	1113	1127	10.1002/humu.22904	127
A Children's Oncology Group and TARGET initiative exploring the genetic landscape of Wilms tumor	Gadd, Samantha; Huff, Vicki; Walz, Amy L.; Ooms, Ariadne H. A. G.; Armstrong, Amy E.; Gerhard, Daniela S.; Smith, Malcolm A.; Auvil, Jaime M. Guidry; Meerzaman, Daoud; Chen, Qing-Rong; Hsu, Chih Hao; Yan, Chunhua; Nguyen, Cu; Hu, Ying; Hermida, Leandro C.; Davidsen, Tanja; Gesuwan, Patee; Ma, Yussanne; Zong, Zusheng; Mungall, Andrew J.; Moore, Richard A.; Marra, Marco A.; Dome, Jeffrey S.; Mullighan, Charles G.; Ma, Jing; Wheeler, David A.; Hampton, Oliver A.; Ross, Nicole; Gastier-Foster, Julie M.; Arold, Stefan T.; Perlman, Elizabeth J.	NATURE GENETICS	OCT 2017	2017	49	10	1487 +		10.1038/ng.3940	123

Kenna, Kevin P.; van Doormaal, Perry T. C.; Dekker, Annelot M.; Ticozzi, Nicola; Kenna, Brendan J.; Diekstra, Frank P.; van Rheenen, Wouter; van Eijk, Kristel R.; Jones, Ashley R.; Keagle, Pamela; Shatunov, Aleksey; Sproviero, William; Smiths, Bradley N.; van Es, Michael A.; Topps, Simon D.; Kenna, Aoife; Miller, Jack W.; Fallini, Claudia; Tiloca, Cinzia; McLaughlin, Russell L.; Vance, Caroline; Troakes, Claire; Colombrita, Claudia; Mora, Gabriele; Calvo, Andrea; Verde, Federico; Al-Sarraj, Safa; King, Andrew; Calini, Daniela; de Bellerocche, Jacqueline; Baas, Frank; van der Kooij, Anneke J.; de Visser, Marianne; ten Asbroek, Anneloor L. M. A.; Sapp, Peter C.; McKenna-Yasek, Diane; Polak, Meraida; Asress, Seneshaw; Luis Munoz-Blanco, Jose; Strom, Tim M.; Meitinger, Thomas; Morrison, Karen E.; Lauria, Giuseppe; Williams, Kelly L.; Leigh, P. Nigel; Nicholson, Garth A.; Blair, Ian P.; Leblond, Claire S.; Dion, Patrick A.; Rouleau, Guy A.; Pall, Hardev; Shaw, Pamela J.; Turner, Martin R.; Talbot, Kevin; Taroni, Franco; Boylan, Kevin B.; Van Blitterswijk, Marka; Rademakers, Rosa; Esteban-Perez, Jesus; Garcia-Redondo, Alberto; Van Damme, Phillip; Robberecht, Wim; Chio, Adrian; Gellera, Cinzia; Drepper, Carsten; Sendtner, Michael; Ratti, Antonia; Glass, Jonathan D.; Mora, Jesus S.; Basak, Nazli A.; Hardiman, Orla; Ludolph, Albert C.; Andersen, Peter M.; Weishaupt, Jochen H.; Brown, Robert H., Jr.; Al-Chalabi, Ammar; Silani, Vincenzo; Shaw, Christopher E.; van den Berg, Leonard H.; Veldink, Jan H.; Landers, John E.; D'Alfonso, Sandra; Mazzini, Letizia; Comi, Giacomo P.; Del Bo, Roberto; Ceroni, Mauro; Gagliardi, Stella; Querin, Giorgia; Bertolin, Cinzia; Pensato, Viviana; Castellotti, Barbara; Corti, Stefania; Cereda, Cristina; Corrado, Lucia; Soraru, Gianni

Comprehensive Functional Annotation of 77 Prostate Cancer Risk Loci	Hazelett, Dennis J.; Rhie, Suhng Kyong; Gaddis, Malaina; Yan, Chunli; Lakeland, Daniel L.; Coetzee, Simon G.; Henderson, Brian E.; Noushmehr, Houtan; Cozen, Wendy; Kote-Jarai, Zsofia; Eeles, Rosalind A.; Easton, Douglas F.; Haiman, Christopher A.; Lu, Wange; Farnham, Peggy J.; Coetzee, Gerhard A.	Ellipse GAME-ON Consortium; Practical Consortium	PLOS GENETICS	JAN 2014	2014	10	1			e1004102 10.1371/journal.pgen.1004102	119
A precise spacing between the NPA domains of aquaporins is essential for silicon permeability in plants	Deshmukh, Rupesh Kailasrao; Vivancos, Julien; Ramakrishnan, Gowsica; Guerin, Valerie; Carpentier, Gabriel; Sonah, Humira; Labbe, Caroline; Isenring, Paul; Belzile, Francois J.; Belanger, Richard R.		PLANT JOURNAL	AUG 2015	2015	83	3	489	500	10.1111/tpj.12904	114
Parallel Compensatory Evolution Stabilizes Plasmids across the Parasitism-Mutualism Continuum	Harrison, Ellie; Guymer, David; Spiers, Andrew J.; Paterson, Steve; Brockhurst, Michael A.		CURRENT BIOLOGY	AUG 3 2015	2015	25	15	2034	2039	10.1016/j.cub.2015.06.024	110
Genetics and the conservation of natural populations: allozymes to genomes	Allendorf, Fred W.		MOLECULAR ECOLOGY	JAN 2017	2017	26	2	420	430	10.1111/mec.13948	108
Targeted sequencing of refractory myeloma reveals a high incidence of mutations in CRBN and Ras pathway genes	Kortum, K. Martin; Mai, Elias K.; Hanafiah, Nur H.; Shi, Chang-Xi; Zhu, Yuan-Xiao; Bruins, Laura; Barrio, Santiago; Jedlowski, Patrick; Merz, Maximilian; Xu, Jing; Stewart, Robert A.; Andrulis, Mindaugas; Jauch, Anna; Hillengass, Jens; Goldschmidt, Hartmut; Bergsagel, P. Leif; Braggio, Esteban; Stewart, A. Keith; Raab, Marc S.		BLOOD	SEP 1 2016	2016	128	9	1226	1233	10.1182/blood-2016-02-698092	106
Settling the score: variant prioritization and Mendelian disease	Eilbeck, Karen; Quinlan, Aaron; Yandell, Mark		NATURE REVIEWS GENETICS	OCT 2017	2017	18	10	599	612	10.1038/nrg.2017.52	105
Genomics advances the study of inbreeding depression in the wild	Kardos, Marty; Taylor, Helen R.; Ellegren, Hans; Luikart, Gordon; Allendorf, Fred W.		EVOLUTIONARY APPLICATIONS	DEC 2016	2016	9	10	1205	1218	10.1111/eva.12414	102

Genomic landscapes of breast fibroepithelial tumors	Tan, Jing; Ong, Choon Kiat; Lim, Weng Khong; Ng, Cedric Chuan Young; Thike, Aye Aye; Ng, Ley Moy; Rajasegaran, Vikneswari; Myint, Swe Swe; Nagarajan, Sanjanaa; Thangaraju, Saranya; Dey, Sucharita; Nasir, Nur Diyana Md; Wijaya, Giovanni Claresta; Lim, Jing Quan; Huang, Dachuan; Li, Zhimei; Wong, Bernice Huimin; Chan, Jason Yong Sheng; McPherson, John R.; Cutcutache, Ioana; Poore, Gregory; Tay, Su Ting; Tan, Wai Jin; Putti, Thomas Choudary; Ahmad, Buhari Shaik; Iau, Philip; Chan, Ching Wan; Tang, Anthony P. H.; Yong, Wei Sean; Madhukumar, Preetha; Ho, Gay Hui; Tan, Veronique Kiak Mien; Wong, Chow Yin; Hartman, Mikael; Ong, Kong Wee; Tan, Benita K. T.; Rozen, Steven G.; Tan, Patrick; Tan, Puay Hoon; Teh, Bin Tean	NATURE GENETICS	NOV 2015	2015	47	11	1341 +	10.1038/ng.3409	101
The genetic basis of parental care evolution in monogamous mice	Bendesky, Andres; Kwon, Young-Mi; Lassance, Jean-Marc; Lewarch, Caitlin L.; Yao, Shenqin; Peterson, Brant K.; He, Meng Xiao; Dulac, Catherine; Hoekstra, Hopi E.	NATURE	APR 27 2017	2017	544	7651	434 +	10.1038/nature22074	100
Novel somatic and germline mutations in intracranial germ cell tumours	Wang, Linghua; Yamaguchi, Shigeru; Burstein, Matthew D.; Terashima, Keita; Chang, Kyle; Ng, Ho-Keung; Nakamura, Hideo; He, Zongxiao; Doddapaneni, Harshavardhan; Lewis, Lora; Wang, Mark; Suzuki, Tomonari; Nishikawa, Ryo; Natsume, Atsushi; Terasaka, Shunsuke; Dauser, Robert; Whitehead, William; Adekunle, Adesina; Sun, Jiayi; Qiao, Yi; Marth, Gabor; Muzny, Donna M.; Gibbs, Richard A.; Leal, Suzanne M.; Wheeler, David A.; Lau, Ching C.	NATURE	JUL 10 2014	2014	511	7508	241 +	10.1038/nature13296	98
A Novel Germline Mutation in BAP1 Predisposes to Familial Clear-Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma	Farley, Megan N.; Schmidt, Laura S.; Mester, Jessica L.; Pena-Llopis, Samuel; Pavia-Jimenez, Andrea; Christie, Alana; Vocke, Cathy D.; Ricketts, Christopher J.; Peterson, James; Middleton, Lindsay; Kinch, Lisa; Grishin, Nick; Merino, Maria J.; Metwalli, Adam R.; Xing, Chao; Xie, Xian-Jin; Dahia, Patricia L. M.; Eng, Charis; Linehan, W. Marston; Brugarolas, James	MOLECULAR CANCER RESEARCH	SEP 2013	2013	11	9	1061 1071	10.1158/1541-7786.MCR-13-0111	98

The African Turquoise Killifish Genome Provides Insights into Evolution and Genetic Architecture of Lifespan	Valenzano, Dario Riccardo; Benayoun, Berenice A.; Singh, Param Priya; Zhang, Elisa; Etter, Paul D.; Hu, Chi-Kuo; Clement-Ziza, Mathieu; Willemsen, David; Cui, Rongfeng; Harel, Itamar; Machado, Ben E.; Yee, Muh-Ching; Sharp, Sabrina C.; Bustamante, Carlos D.; Beyer, Andreas; Johnson, Eric A.; Brunet, Anne	CELL	DEC 6 2015	2015	163	6	1539	1554	10.1016/j.cell.2015.11.008	95
Comparative Functional Analysis of DPYD Variants of Potential Clinical Relevance to Dihydropyrimidine Dehydrogenase Activity	Offer, Steven M.; Fossum, Croix C.; Wegner, Natalie J.; Stuflesser, Alexander J.; Butterfield, Gabriel L.; Diasio, Robert B.	CANCER RESEARCH	MAY 1 2014	2014	74	9	2545	2554	10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-13-2482	94
Clinical and pathological impact of VHL, PBRM1, BAP1, SETD2, KDM6A, and JARID1c in clear cell renal cell carcinoma	Gossage, Lucy; Murtaza, Muhammed; Slatter, Andrew F.; Lichtenstein, Conrad P.; Warren, Anne; Haynes, Beverley; Marass, Francesco; Roberts, Ian; Shanahan, Susan J.; Claas, Andreas; Dunham, Andrew; May, Andrew P.; Rosenfeld, Nitzan; Forshew, Tim; Eisen, Tim	GENES CHROMOSOMES & CANCER	JAN 2014	2014	53	1	38	51	10.1002/gcc.22116	93
The genetic landscape of endometrial clear cell carcinomas	DeLair, Deborah F.; Burke, Kathleen A.; Selenica, Pier; Lim, Raymond S.; Scott, Sasinya N.; Middha, Sumit; Mohanty, Abhinata S.; Cheng, Donavan T.; Berger, Michael F.; Soslow, Robert A.; Weigelt, Britta	JOURNAL OF PATHOLOGY	OCT 2017	2017	243	2	230	241	10.1002/path.4947	92
Somatic aberrations of mismatch repair genes as a cause of microsatellite-unstable cancers	Geurts-Giele, Willemina R. R.; Leenen, Celine H. M.; Dubbink, Hendrikus J.; Meijssen, Isabelle C.; Post, Edward; Sleddens, Hein F. B. M.; Kuipers, Ernst J.; Goverde, Anne; van den Ouweland, Ans M. W.; van Lier, Margot G. F.; Steyerberg, Ewout W.; van Leerdam, Monique E.; Wagner, Anja; Dinjens, Winand N. M.	JOURNAL OF PATHOLOGY	DEC 2014	2014	234	4	548	559	10.1002/path.4419	92
Mutations in IFT172 cause isolated retinal degeneration and Bardet-Biedl syndrome	Bujakowska, Kinga M.; Zhang, Qi; Siemiatkowska, Anna M.; Liu, Qin; Place, Emily; Falk, Marni J.; Consugar, Mark; Lancelot, Marie-Elise; Antonio, Aline; Lonjou, Christine; Carpentier, Wassila; Mohand-Said, Saddek; den Hollander, Anneke I.; Cremers, Frans P. M.; Leroy, Bart P.; Gai, Xiaowu; Sahel, Jose-Alain; van den Born, L. Ingeborgh; Collin, Rob W. J.; Zeitz, Christina; Audo, Isabelle; Pierce, Eric A.	HUMAN MOLECULAR GENETICS	JAN 1 2015	2015	24	1	230	242	10.1093/hmg/ddu441	90

Genomic and functional analyses of Mycobacterium tuberculosis strains implicate ald in D-cycloserine resistance	Desjardins, Christopher A.; Cohen, Keira A.; Munsamy, Vanisha; Abeel, Thomas; Maharaj, Kashmeel; Walker, Bruce J.; Shea, Terrance P.; Almeida, Deepak V.; Manson, Abigail L.; Salazar, Alex; Padayatchi, Nesri; O'Donnell, Max R.; Mlisana, Koleka P.; Wortman, Jennifer; Birren, Bruce W.; Grosset, Jacques; Earl, Ashlee M.; Pym, Alexander S.		NATURE GENETICS	MAY 2016	2016	48	5	544	+	10.1038/ng.3548	86	
Molecular-defined clonal evolution in patients with chronic myeloid leukemia independent of the BCR-ABL status	Schmidt, M.; Rinke, J.; Schaefer, V.; Schnittger, S.; Kohlmann, A.; Obstfelder, E.; Kunert, C.; Ziermann, J.; Winkelmann, N.; Eigendorff, E.; Haferlach, T.; Haferlach, C.; Hochhaus, A.; Ernst, T.		LEUKEMIA	DEC 2014	2014	28	12	2292	2299	10.1038/leu.2014.272	86	
RNF213 Rare Variants in an Ethnically Diverse Population With Moyamoya Disease	Cecchi, Alana C.; Guo, Dongchuan; Ren, Zhao; Flynn, Kelly; Santos-Cortez, Regie Lyn P.; Leal, Suzanne M.; Wang, Gao T.; Regalado, Ellen S.; Steinberg, Gary K.; Shendure, Jay; Bamshad, Michael J.; Grotta, James C.; Nickerson, Deborah A.; Pannu, Hariyadarshi; Milewicz, Dianna M.	Univ Washington	STROKE	NOV 2014	2014	45	11	3200	3207	10.1161/STROKEAHA.114.006244	85	
Benchmarking mutation effect prediction algorithms using functionally validated cancer-related missense mutations	Martelotto, Luciano G.; Ng, Charlotte K. Y.; De Filippo, Maria R.; Zhang, Yan; Piscuoglio, Salvatore; Lim, Raymond S.; Shen, Ronglai; Norton, Larry; Reis-Filho, Jorge S.; Weigelt, Britta		GENOME BIOLOGY		2014	2014	15	10		484 10.1186/s13059-014-0484-1	83	
Evaluation of in silico algorithms for use with ACMG/AMP clinical variant interpretation guidelines	Ghosh, Rajarshi; Oak, Ninad; Plon, Sharon E.		GENOME BIOLOGY	NOV 28 2017		2017	18			225 10.1186/s13059-017-1353-5	82	
JAK3 mutants transform hematopoietic cells through JAK1 activation, causing T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia in a mouse model	Degryse, Sandrine; de Bock, Charles E.; Cox, Luk; Demeyer, Sofie; Gielen, Olga; Mentens, Nicole; Jacobs, Kris; Geerdens, Ellen; Gianfelici, Valentina; Hulselmans, Gert; Fiers, Mark; Aerts, Stein; Meijerink, Jules P.; Tousseyn, Thomas; Cools, Jan		BLOOD	NOV 13 2014		2014	124	20	3092	3100	10.1182/blood-2014-04-566687	80
UMD-Predictor: A High-Throughput Sequencing Compliant System for Pathogenicity Prediction of any Human cDNA Substitution	Salgado, David; Desvignes, Jean-Pierre; Rai, Ghadi; Blanchard, Arnaud; Miltgen, Morgane; Pinard, Amelie; Levy, Nicolas; Collod-Beroud, Gwenaelle; Beroud, Christophe		HUMAN MUTATION	MAY 2016		2016	37	5	439	446	10.1002/humu.22965	78
Positive and purifying selection in mitochondrial genomes of a bird with mitonuclear discordance	Morales, Hernan E.; Pavlova, Alexandra; Joseph, Leo; Sunnucks, Paul		MOLECULAR ECOLOGY	JUN 2015		2015	24	11	2820	2837	10.1111/mec.13203	78

Mutation Update for Kabuki Syndrome Genes KMT2D and KDM6A and Further Delineation of X-Linked Kabuki Syndrome Subtype 2	Boegershausen, Nina; Gatinois, Vincent; Riehmer, Vera; Kayserili, Huelya; Becker, Jutta; Thoenes, Michaela; Simsek-Kiper, Pelin OEzlem; Barat-Houari, Mouna; Elcioglu, Nursel H.; Wieczorek, Dagmar; Tinschert, Sigrid; Sarrabay, Guillaume; Strom, Tim M.; Fabre, Aurelie; Baynam, Gareth; Sanchez, Elodie; Nuernberg, Gudrun; Altunoglu, Umut; Capri, Yline; Isidor, Bertrand; Lacombe, Didier; Corsini, Carole; Cormier-Daire, Valerie; Sanlaville, Damien; Giuliano, Fabienne; Le Quan Sang, Kim-Hanh; Kayirangwa, Honorine; Nuernberg, Peter; Meitinger, Thomas; Boduroglu, Koray; Zoll, Barbara; Lyonnet, Stanislas; Tzschach, Andreas; Verloes, Alain; Di Donato, Nataliya; Tuitou, Isabelle; Netzer, Christian; Li, Yun; Genevieve, David; Yigit, Goekhan; Wollnik, Bernd	HUMAN MUTATION	SEP 2016	2016	37	9	847	864	10.1002/humu.23026	75
Functional annotation of colon cancer risk SNPs	Yao, Lijing; Tak, Yu Gyoung; Berman, Benjamin P.; Farnham, Peggy J.	NATURE COMMUNICATIONS	SEP 2014	2014	5			5114	10.1038/ncomms6114	75
Candidate gene association studies: a comprehensive guide to useful in silico tools	Patnala, Radhika; Clements, Judith; Batra, Jyotsna	BMC GENETICS	MAY 9 2013	2013	14			39	10.1186/1471-2156-14-39	75

Average per Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1377.43	0	0	71	382	850	1281	1919	2690	2447

148 0 0 7 48 107 125 192 266 291

107 4 49 117 165 158 108 95 89 71

127.2 0 0 0 0 21 105 148 223 139

104 0 0 0 11 43 115 135 177 143

106.8 0 0 0 0 32 70 129 155 148

81.33 0 0 0 17 50 71 109 121 120

27.56 0 19 25 27 29 34 49 40 25

22.22 0 20 27 24 28 25 28 22 26

27.86 0 0 12 37 44 32 33 21 16

26.29 0 0 3 20 27 30 42 32 30

29.5 0 0 0 25 38 28 25 35 26

24.43 0 0 0 21 34 29 33 36 18

19.88 0 0 14 26 22 22 31 26 18

19 0 8 25 22 28 24 11 18 16

37.75 0 0 0 0 0 18 39 51 43

20 0 0 14 25 12 20 34 21 14

21.5 0 0 0 0 10 36 30 36 17

21.17 0 0 0 1 15 24 23 29 35

18.14 0 0 0 23 21 24 16 24 19

24.6 0 0 0 0 2 21 37 37 26

19.83 0 0 0 1 25 28 18 28 19

14.88 0 5 19 23 20 14 17 11 10

16.29 0 0 0 11 16 8 26 28 25

15.71 0 0 1 10 14 19 20 26 20

21.6 0 0 0 0 3 16 30 25 34

17.67 0 0 0 0 11 20 26 28 21

21 0 0 0 0 1 24 31 31 18

17 0 0 0 0 11 17 22 25 27

14.43 0 0 0 19 19 15 14 20 14

20 0 0 0 0 14 26 21 22 17

12.25 0 2 17 20 13 17 13 8 8

10.89 1 11 21 16 12 14 10 6 7

13.57 0 0 1 14 13 15 19 17 16

11.75 0 2 9 16 15 17 9 14 12

11.63 0 5 18 16 19 11 5 14 5

18.4 0 0 0 0 0 19 25 21 27

11.5 0 0 5 18 16 15 14 14 10

12.86 0 1 9 16 21 12 12 9 10

14.33 0 0 0 4 20 18 19 17 8

10.75 0 0 4 11 18 11 16 14 12

10.63 0 0 4 19 17 11 14 11 9

10.38 0 0 5 21 13 15 16 7 6

16.4 0 0 0 0 1 12 26 22 21

10 0 1 11 13 9 14 12 9 11

13 0 0 0 8 9 19 15 16 11

11.14 0 0 3 8 18 15 16 12 6

12.5 0 0 0 2 10 14 16 20 13

9.38 0 0 11 18 13 13 9 8 3

8.33 0 7 10 10 13 7 9 16 3
